

north american
academic research

Research

Factors that Contribute to the Objective and Subjective Career Success of Project Managers

Shilimi Moono^{1}, Yibin Li²*

¹*MBA Student, Department of Management and Economics, Chang'An University, Xi'an, Shaanxi Province, China*

²*Associate Professor at Chang'An University, Doctor/Post doctorate, and Master's Lecturer, Department of Logistics and Management, Chang'An University, Xi'an, Shaanxi Province, China*

**Corresponding author*

Accepted : 12 August, 2019 ;Online: 14 August, 2019

DOI : <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3367810>

Abstract : Career success is the main focus of career scholars as well as organizational stakeholders. Historically, career success has been conceptualized and measured objectively, mainly as salary, rank, or number of promotions. However, the changing nature of work has also necessitated a change in the way many employees view success, adding a more subjective component. Although there has been theoretical discussion and calls to develop a comprehensive measure of subjective career success, no contemporary comprehensive quantitative measure exists. The goal of this study was to highlight the factors that contribute to the objective career success as well as the subjective career success of project managers.

Keywords : Project Manager, Objective career success (OCS), Subjective career success (SCS)

Introduction

In new and expanding fields like electronics, nucleonic, astronautics, avionics, and cryogenics, a new type of manager is being bred. Although he goes by many titles, the one most generally used is the project manager. His role in the modern industry deserves more scrutiny than it has received from students of management and professional managers. Generally speaking, the project manager's business is to create a product — a piece of advanced technology hardware. The primary tool available to him is the brainpower of men who are professional specialists in diverse fields. He uses this tool in all the phases of the

creation of his product, from concept through the initial test operation and manufacturing stages.

To be called a project, an undertaking must meet a specific set of conditions. If an undertaking meets those conditions, then it must follow the prescribed project management methodology defined by the organization. In the last 10 years, project management has undergone significant change. Rather than having just one approach, you now have a variety of approaches, all based on the characteristics of the project. So in effect, the uniqueness of the project translates into the uniqueness of the best-fit approach for managing it (Wysocki 2012).

Traditionally, the career of a project manager was confined to advancing in organizational hierarchies the focus nowadays lays on objective and subjective aspects. Moreover, within the boundary, fewer careers individuals not only strive for climbing up the ladder but rather for a life career including satisfaction within their professional and private sphere. Despite the fact that the literature on careers has not found a common ground to define and operationalize career success (Abele-Brehm and Stief, 2004; Dette, Abele and Renner, 2004), the objective/subjective dichotomy is widely accepted in the career literature (Abele-Brehm and Stief, 2004; Abele and Spurk, 2009b). While objective career measures are neutral and measurement does not highly differ across the literature, subjective success can be assessed in various ways. Thus the present discussion paper will present various valid measures of both.

Literature Review

Project Management

To put project management into perspective, you need a definition — a common starting point. All too often, people call any work they have to do a "project." Projects have a very specific definition. If a set of tasks or work to be done does not meet the strict definition, then it cannot be called a project. By definition, a project is a sequence of unique, complex, and connected activities that have one goal or purpose and that must be completed by a specific time, within budget, and according to specification (Wysocki 2012).

The Project Management Institute (PMI) formally defines project management as follows: "The application of knowledge, skills, tools, and techniques to project activities to meet the project requirements". In a single sentence, a project manager is a professional in the field of project management. Project managers have the responsibility of the planning,

procurement, and execution of a project, in any undertaking that has a defined scope, defined start, and a defined finish; regardless of industry (Project Management Institute, 2008).

Unique Characteristics

A project is an organizational unit dedicated to the attainment of a goal — generally the successful completion of a developmental product on time, within budget, and in conformance with predetermined performance specifications. The project staff will be a "mix" of brainpower, varying with the project's mission. For example, a project involving a high degree of development, such as one devoted to achieving a practical demonstration of ionic propulsion that can later be applied in rocketry, will have a high proportion of scientists to engineers and a high proportion of theoretically inclined personnel. In contrast, a project committed to attaining a successful full-power trial of a propulsion engine utilizing a proven solid propellant will have more engineers than scientists. Projects are typically organized by task (vertical structure) instead of by function (horizontal organization). The relative advantages of "project" and "systems" organizations have been the subject of widespread controversy, and it is not my intent here to elaborate on this issue. The obvious organizational goal is to seek the advantages of both — the vertical structure in which the control and performance associated with autonomous management are maintained for a given project, and the horizontal in which better continuity, flexibility, and use of scarce talents may be achieved in a technical group.

A study of the project manager function must examine these topics: what he does, what he must be, and what training he needs. In considering these, I shall limit myself to the more or less autonomous project in which "real" management and personnel responsibility reside with the project manager. This autonomy is in contrast to the organization in which the project function is maintained by a "project engineer," who often is relegated to a staff position with responsibilities far outweighing his authority, and who must pursue tenuous relationships with a great deal of skill and persistence to achieve even modest goals.

As the foregoing may suggest, life is not dull for a project manager. He is the man in between management and the technologist — the one man in the organization who must be at home in the front office talking about budgets, time schedules, and corporate policies and at home in the laboratory talking about technical research and development problems. But he is not a superman. He cannot be expected to double as a member of the executive committee and as a scientist equally well. Being a little of both, he is different from both — and it is precisely this quality which makes him so valuable. In his own right he does what neither the

front-office executive nor the scientists can do: accomplish the aims of his corporate management, while serving as a perpetual buffer so that the engineers and scientists can meet the technological objectives that only they can define and only their output can meet. Therefore, the job is an unusual one.

In addition to his everyday job of keeping the work moving, the project manager should put a good deal of thought into planning. The crux of the effective performance of any project lies in the interrelationship between organizational structure and individuals. The art of organization planning involves the correct tailoring of organizational structure to available individuals and vice versa. An often-repeated thought in the literature of scientific administration is that although the organizational structure of a project is important, if not vital, it will not make up for inadequate caliber of technologists in the organization. On the other hand, poor organization structure can tie up the output of top-notch engineers and scientists. In advanced-technology industries, sound organization planning requires adroitness in recruiting scarce talent both from within and without the parent organization. It also involves the ability to utilize engineers and scientists who in some cases do not measure up to reasonable requirements for the project — the ability to shape a team which can "play over its head" when it has to. Sound organization

Advance planning in a project cannot be done without a thorough understanding of the personalities, the characteristics, and the attitudes of all the technologists, both as individuals and as members of their particular professional methodologies. Planning is vital in a project. In this area, an important duty of the project manager is to avoid the crises that often manifest themselves during the design, manufacturing, and checkout stages. Perfection will never be attained, and the best efforts of the manager can serve only to reduce, never to eliminate these crises. Still, planning pays for itself many times over. While technological crises have become accepted as an inherent part of our advanced technology projects, it must always be realized that each of these crucial periods leaves residual effects throughout the remaining course of the project.

Thus, the resolution of such a crisis generally involves a sacrifice of engineering principle for expediency, which may, in turn, lead to subsequent crises. Further, each crisis, with its resultant need for an immediate solution, erodes the constructive attitude of the project's engineers and scientists, particularly the theoreticians. Therefore, the more that can

be done to avoid these situations in advance, the better. It is, unfortunately, true that most crises that arise during a project can be traced to a lack of adequate planning.

At any time during the project, the manager may be called on to act as frontman to help shape or reshape the policies that affect his project relative to the corporate structure and the company's development objectives. Contrary to many opinions about the advanced-technology industries, "selling" is a never-ending job of a project manager, as it is of most other senior managers in the corporate organization. In matters of acquiring scarce funds, people, and materials, the project manager must always be able to make an effective presentation, often on short notice. Many project managers have suddenly found themselves, in mid-course, fighting for the very existence of their project. While the outcome of many such struggles is often beyond the influence of any actions taken by the manager, it is true that in numerous other cases his actions as a fully informed representative of the project will have a profound influence on the outcome.

Qualifications for success

Some of the qualifications that a successful project manager must possess proceed logically from the preceding discussion:

- (1) His career must have been molded in the advanced technology environment.
- (2) He must have a working knowledge of many fields of science, the fundamental kind of knowledge which he can augment when necessary to delve into the intricacies of a specific technology.
- (3) He must have a good understanding of general management problems —, especially marketing, control, contract work, purchasing, law, and personnel administration. The concept of profitability should be familiar to him.
- (4) He must have a strong, continuous, active interest in teaching, training, and developing his supervisors.

In reviewing these qualifications, one can observe the emphasis on the integrative function in the operations of the project manager. There is an ever-present requirement for the joining of many parts into a systematic whole. Describing the processes by which the integrative mind works is, of course, difficult, for they are largely indefinable, just as the requisite qualities for managerial personnel are not subject to scientific definition. It is clear, however, that the integrative mind must deal with intangible factors as well as the tangible, and that there is need also at times for an intuitive process in the formulation of judgment and decision.

(especially where men's reactions are an important factor). It is perhaps in this respect that the outlook of a good project manager differs most sharply from that of the researcher:

The methodology of scientific analysis and experimentation has been carefully developed over many years and is a part of the indoctrination of young men in training for a scientific career. This indoctrination breeds distrust of intuition and a tendency to disregard intangibles. Further, the analytical mind will not draw its hypothesis until all relevant data have been observed and interpreted. If a hypothesis must be drawn before this, it must be thoroughly qualified and hedged in the interests of scientific accuracy. In project organizations, it is recognized that the analytical mind produces the concepts by which the project advances toward its goal. But without the integrative function, often nothing would be done with the concepts originating in the analytical function. The topnotch manager of an advanced technology project must be capable of both integration and analysis and must understand that the rigorous training of professional technologists with its emphasis on analysis sometimes impairs their integrative ability.

Defining careers

Before diving into the concept of career success, it is imperative to provide our working definition of a career. We invoke Hall's (1976, p. 4) explanation of a career as "the individually-perceived sequence of attitudes and behaviors associated with work-related experiences and activities throughout a person's life." This definition allows us to consider work-related experiences in contemporary society, where individuals are becoming less bound to a single organization. Likewise, it does not limit the career to upward advancement or only professional occupations, as previous, historical definitions have (Greenhaus, 2003). Thus, in the remainder of this paper, any mention of career success is made about this broader and encompassing the definition of a career.

Defining career success

Career success is defined by Arthur et al. (2005) as the "accomplishment of desirable work-related outcomes at any point in a person's work experiences over time" (p. 179). As previously noted, career success encompasses both objective and subjective criteria (Hughes, 1958). The literature generally coalesces on the definition of the objective criteria as that which is directly observable and thus easily measured and verified. Objective career success typically relies on "landmarks" that can be readily compared across people as a means of judgment for success (e.g., Arthur et al., 2005; Abele & Wiese, 2008; Heslin, 2005; Hughes, 1958). Definitions for subjective success are considerably vaguer, including "a self-

evaluation of career progress" (offered by Arthur et al., 2005, p. 179, based on Stebbins, 1970), "individual's subjective apprehension and evaluation of his or her career" (Van Maanen, 1977, p. 9), "individuals' perceptual evaluations of, and affective reactions to, their careers" (offered by Ng and Feldman, 2014, p. 170, based on Greenhaus et al., 1990; Turban and Dougherty, 1994).

These definitions can be interpreted in two ways. First, they suggest that people form an overall subjective evaluation of their career success, which may or may not be driven by objective factors. Second, the definitions imply that there are additional components to career success beyond objective factors that require subjective evaluation (i.e., cannot be retrieved from a standard organizational database). Based on several modern career theories, we argue that a person's career success is driven by objective factors in addition to those that are less tangible and require subjective interpretation. We aim to identify these core subjective factors and create a means to measure them and facilitate comparisons across individuals. In the following sections, we describe how career theories support the inclusion of subjective factors beyond an overall subjective appraisal. Next, we discuss how SCS has been operationalized in the literature to date, highlighting the deficiencies of these operationalizations as a means of assessing SCS (Shockley, Ureksoy, Rodopman, Poteat, & Dullaghan, 2016).

Objective Career Success

The number of black people occupying managerial positions in the United States has grown considerably in recent years. The percentage of minority groups increased from 3.6 percent of the national total in 1977 to 5.2 percent in 1982 (Jones, 1986), and in 1986 blacks represented 6 percent of all managers (Williams, 1987). Despite these recent gains, however, many observers have commented on the presence of an invisible barrier, or "glass ceiling" that prevents blacks (as well as members of the other minority groups and women) from advancing beyond lower- or middle-management positions (Crotty & Timmons, 1974; Davis & Watson, 1982; Dickens & Dickens 1982; DiTomaso, Thompson, & Blake, 1986; Jones, 1986; Morrison, White & Van Velsor, 1987). Thus, although blacks have gained greater access to managerial jobs, there is still cause for concern that black managers may face "treatment discrimination."

Unlike "access discrimination," which prevents members of a subgroup of the population from entering a job or an organization, treatment discrimination occurs when subgroup members receive fewer rewards, resources, or opportunities on the job than they

legitimately deserve based on job-related criteria. Thus such discrimination represents a situation in which the treatment of the employees is based more on their subgroup membership than on their merit or achievements (Levitin, Quinn & Staines, 1971). Treatment discrimination can affect not only such tangible phenomena as position assignments, training opportunities, salary increases, promotions, terminations, and layoffs but also such subtle issues as acceptance into a workgroup or the availability of career-enhancing and psychosocial support from supervisors and others (Ilgen & Youtz, 1986). In effect, subgroup members who are exposed to treatment discrimination encounter organizational experiences members of a dominant group encounter within an organization.

In an early theoretical examination of organizational discrimination, Kanter (1979) argued that minority members, women, and other token employees have low access to opportunity and power within organizations. She viewed opportunities as growth prospects stemming from a present job and suggested that employees with restricted opportunities ultimately lower their aspirations and commitment and engage in behaviors that reinforce negative opinions about their potential contributions to an organization. Additionally, restricted access to power – through routine task assignments or exclusion from informal social networks – produces a cycle of disadvantage for minority members who are unable to influence organizational actions or the course of their careers (Kanter, 1979). Kanter suggested that the provision of less favorable experiences and opportunities for minority employees than for nonminority employees indicated institutional racism in organizations.

Much of the prior empirical research on treatment discrimination has focused on the experiences of working women. There is evidence of discrimination against women in compensation (Levitin et al., 1971; Terborg & Ilgen, 1975), access to authority and responsibility on the job (Olson & Becker, 1983; Stewart & Gudykunst, 1975), access to authority and responsibility on the job (Harlan & Weiss, 1982; Wolf & Fligstein, 1979), and opportunities to cultivate developmental relationships with mentors, sponsors, and peers (Fernandez, 1981; Rosen, Templeton, & Kichline, 1981).

Applying the research findings on gender discrimination to racial minorities, Ilgen and Youtz (1986) suggested that minority members may experience treatment discrimination in many respects and that such unfavorable experiences can have dysfunctional consequences for their career success. Specifically, those authors posited that treatment discrimination experienced by minorities may reduce their job performance and career prospects since they would receive fewer opportunities to enhance work-related skills and develop supportive

relationships within an organization than other employees. These lost opportunities, which may be reflected in the absence of a powerful sponsor or the assignment of routine tasks, can depress minority employees' ability, motivation, or both, and thereby diminish the effectiveness of their job performance. In effect, Ilgen and Youtz (1986) proposed that race differences in job performance can be explained – at least by the differential treatment people in different groups' experience. Those authors further suggested that minority members may internalize an organization's negative evaluations of them and engage "self-limiting behaviors" – for example, refusing a challenging job assignment or declining an opportunity for additional training – that perpetuate performance difference between minority and nonminority employees.

There is considerable evidence that raters evaluate the job performance of blacks less favorable than the job performance of whites, especially when the raters are themselves white (Kraiger & Ford, 1985). There is also evidence that black managers experience restricted advancement opportunities (Alderfer, Alderfer, Tucker, & Tucker, 1980; Brown & Ford, 1977; Fernandez, 1975; Irons & Moore, 1985; Nixon, 1985a) and report extensive dissatisfaction and frustration with their careers (Fernandez, 1975; Jones 1986). However, the role of organizational experiences in producing these negative outcomes remains largely unexplored.

Career theories and subjective career success

Several modern career theories suggest that for many people, career success extends beyond traditional objective factors. Moreover, many of these theorists suggest that SCS is multifaceted. For example, Hall (1976) proposed the concept of the protean career, highlighting the importance of flexibility, freedom, continuous learning, and intrinsic rewards for many people navigating the modern career landscape. Arthur and Rousseau (1996) introduced the boundaryless career, defined as a career that is independent of traditional organizational career arrangements with a single organization (DeFillippi & Arthur, 1996). Subsequent research on the topic suggests that certain factors are more important to success in those with a boundaryless mindset, such as learning and development (Granrose & Baccili, 2006) and work-life conflict (Wille, De Fruyt, & Feys, 2013). Lastly, the kaleidoscope career model (Mainiero & Sullivan, 2006) describes how people change the path of their career to match different aspects of their lives both inside and outside of work. The authors explicitly highlight the role of three key motivators: authenticity, challenge, and work-life balance.

Thus, although these theoretical perspectives differ to some extent in their focus, the idea that success has an internal evaluative component based on multiple criteria is a consistent theme.

Career satisfaction

The most common representation of SCS is found in Greenhaus, Parasuraman, and Wormley's (1990) career satisfaction measure (Heslin, 2005; Ng et al., 2005; Zhou, Sun, Guan, Li, & Pan, 2013). This scale assesses satisfaction regarding progress toward personal career goals in four areas: overall career, income, advancement, and new skills. As previously discussed, there are many other factors beyond satisfaction that researchers have noted as important to SCS. Satisfaction seems to be an important component of SCS, but alone, it is a deficient measure of the concept (Heslin, 2003, 2005).

Overall success perceptions

Measures of overall success perceptions, such as Turban and Dougherty's (1994) scale, align with the first interpretation of SCS offered above—that people form an overall assessment of their career based on their subjective interpretation. While useful in its own right, this perspective lacks information about subjective factors that drive the overall assessment of success. As such, measures of this nature may not provide a comprehensive assessment of the construct, nor may they account for as much variance in the true score as would a multidimensional measure.

Methodology

Multidimensional approaches

Numerous researchers have proposed multidimensional models of SCS founded on qualitative research. As a precursor to the development of the SCS, a review of existing SCS measures based on qualitative research was compiled (see Table 2). The studies were identified by conducting a PsycINFO database search, reviewing the reference sections of career success articles, and from a review piece (Dries, 2011). Common themes were identified (quality of work/performance, relationships/influence on others, financial factors, advancement, life beyond work, growth, and learning, autonomy, satisfaction, respect/recognition, and having an impact/meaning), and dimensions from each measure were classified into one or more of these themes.

Table 1. Commonly used existing measures of subjective career success.

<i>Study</i>	Measures
<i>Gattiker&Larwood (1986)</i>	Job success
	1. I am receiving positive feedback about my performance from all quarters
	2. I am offered opportunities for further education by my employer.
	3. I have enough responsibility on my job.
	4. I am fully backed my managers in my work.
	5. I am in a job which offers me the chance to learn new skills.
	6. I am most happy when I am at work.
	7. I am dedicated to my work.
	8. I am in a position to do mostly work which I really like.
	Interpersonal success
	9. I am respected by my peers.
	10. I am getting good performance evaluations.
	11. I am accepted by my peers.
	12. I have my superior's confidence
	Financial success
	13. I am receiving fair compensation compared to my peers.
	14. I am drawing a high income compared to my peers.
	15. I am earning as much as I think my work is worth.
	Hierarchical success
	16. I am pleased with the promotions I have received so far.
	17. I am reaching my career goals within the time frame I set for myself.
	18. I am in a job which offers promotional opportunities.
Life success	
19. I am happy with my private life.	
20. I am enjoying my non-work activities.	
21. I am satisfied with my life overall.	
22. I am dedicated to my work.	
<i>Greenhaus, Parasuraman, &Wormley (1990)</i>	I am satisfied with...
	1...the success I have achieved in my career.
	2...the progress I have made toward meeting my overall career goals.
	3...the progress I have made toward meeting my goals for income.
	4... the progress I have made toward meeting my goals for advancement
5... the progress I have made toward meeting my goals for the development of new skills.	
<i>Turban and</i>	1. How successful has your career been?

<i>Dougherty (1994)</i>	
	2. Compared to your coworkers, how successful is your career?
	3. How successful does your significant other feel your career has been?
	4. Given your age, do you think that your career is on schedule, or ahead or behind schedule?

Greenhaus, Parasuraman, and Wormley conducted a comprehensive survey on objective career success that was distributed through company mail to each manager selected to participate in the study. Participation was voluntary and assured each participant that their responses would be treated as confidential. Preliminary analysis revealed that race was unrelated to age, organizational tenure, job function, or organizational level in any of the surveyed companies, thereby indicating that the matching process was successful in producing demographically similar samples of blacks and whites.

The managers in this section of the study represented diverse job functions within three organizations and a wide range of managerial, professional, and supervisory positions. Their educational and salary levels suggested that most of the managers studied held lower to middle-level management and professional positions. The diversity of job functions and the high response rates suggest that the respondent group represented the population of black managers. Perhaps most importantly, the black and white managers were comparable in terms of age, organizational tenure, job function, and organizational level.

The measures were race and gender, organizational experiences, job performance evaluations, and career outcomes. The results showed correlations that reveal that black managers reported having less job discretion and lower feelings of acceptance than white managers. Also, blacks were rated lower on both dimensions of job performance, received lower promotion assessments, were more likely to be at career plateaus, and were more dissatisfied with their careers than white.

Based on this review of the literature, the goal of the present study is to create and validate a multidimensional measure of SCS that extends beyond satisfaction and represents meaningful dimensions of success in the modern career landscape. In doing so, we acknowledge that individual definitions of career success are complex and highly personal. While we believe there is space in the literature for a comprehensive measure, we accept that one predefined measure can never entirely capture this complexity. However, in the interest of producing a means for quantitative assessment that facilitates comparison, prediction, and generalization across populations, we believe the development of such a measure is merited.

Additionally, Social Cognitive Career Theory points out a positive reciprocal relationship between career outcomes and self-efficacy, generally defined as the beliefs people have about their abilities to complete a task. Self-efficacy has been applied to specific domains, including occupational and career self-efficacy. By applying this concept to the SCS domain, researchers have found that perceptions of SCS (operationalized as overall self-referent and other-referent success perceptions) positively relate to one's occupational self-efficacy, which in turn relates to continued success.

Discussion

The second part of this study aimed to examine relationships among race, organizational experiences, job performance evaluations, and career outcomes. In particular, the research sought to determine whether organizational experiences mediated race differences in job performance evaluations mediated race differences in career outcomes. Significant race effects were observed for both job performance dimensions: supervisors rated blacks lower than whites on both relationship and task components of performance.

Ilgén and Youtz (1986) suggested that the differential treatment minority members experience may explain race differences in job performance. The finding that a portion of the race effect on job performance operated indirectly through job discretion and acceptance provides some support for this assertion. Thus, the less favorable job evaluation received by black managers is partially attributable to the lower levels of job discretion blacks experience and their lower-level organizational acceptance. The results of the study by Greenhaus, Parasuraman, and Wormley strengthen the conclusion that blacks may be excluded from opportunities for power and integration within organizations and that such exclusion may be detrimental to their job performance.

The effect of race on career plateauing was predominantly direct. Moreover, the impact of race on plateau status is not likely to be an artifact of the sampling procedure here, since the black and the white managers were similar in age, organizational tenure, job function, and organizational level. Also, although it has been argued that blacks are assigned to dead-end jobs, the study data does not support that assertion. Career path elasticity was measured to determine the assessment of the extent to which the previous incumbent of a particular position has been mobile within an organization. Future research should examine the extent to which race differences in career plateauing are due to organizational decisions to keep a manager in a specific position as opposed to managers' decisions to remain in their jobs.

The race had a small indirect effect on career satisfaction. One reason blacks reported lower career satisfaction than whites were because the blacks perceived less discretion and autonomy in their jobs than whites. However, the direct effect of race on career satisfaction overwhelmed the indirect effect. Additional research needs to identify the determinants of career satisfaction so that race differences in career satisfaction can be better understood. Since the career concept is ultimately related to time, perhaps time-related variables like attainment of career goals and promotion history would be potent predictors of career satisfaction and would provide a deeper understanding of race differences in career satisfaction.

The role of meaningful work has been mentioned by several scholars (e.g., Cochran, 1990; Olson & Shultz, 2013; Praskova, Hood, & Creed, 2014) and is a dimension frequently uncovered in qualitative work conducted in the past 10 years. Why this dimension of success has emerged as important over time is unclear, particularly given that nationally representative research shows the importance of altruistic values across generations is slightly decreasing (Twenge, Campbell, Hoffman, & Lance, 2010), despite much anecdotal and popular press statements to the contrary. Nonetheless, conceptualizations of success and values are distinct concepts; it is possible that employees do not realize the value of finding purpose or meaning in their work, but when it is achieved, it has wide-reaching implications for career attitudes and well-being. Overall, the results of the analysis of the relative weight highlight the importance of considering the individual dimensions of the SCS as well as the global construct. In the present study, we aimed to create an overall measure that aims to incorporate many facets of success, but depending on the purpose of the study, future researchers may wish to extend the items for each dimension to create stand-alone measures. This could be useful in understanding, for example, how certain personality or human capital variables predict specific SCS dimensions.

Besides, career commitment is, by definition, self-focused on the individual's career, but it is related to other concepts with direct implications for the organization, including job satisfaction, job involvement, organizational commitment, and withdrawal intentions. Thus, by aiming to design jobs such that they support the achievement of success in the eight identified domains, organizations may be able to positively influence career commitment, productivity, and tenure.

As career success is a topic of considerable research interest, a plethora of studies has been conducted examining its predictors, correlates, and taxonomies. Given the limited scope

of preexisting career success conceptualizations, I believe that the first step for future research is a re-examination of these topics, as this would be informative for both theory building and applied research efforts. For example, it would be interesting to see if the pattern of relationships confirmed in previous meta-analytic research where SCS was operationalized as career satisfaction is consistent with the SCS. Along the same lines, exploration of gender differences with the new measure may uncover some important distinctions, particularly since there are known gender gaps in objective factors (salary and promotion) in favor of men.

The use of personal definitions of career success as an individual difference variable opens a wide array of research paths to explore, such as its relationship with other work attitudes, work-life balance, or performance. Examination of how success perceptions are formed and how they change over time would be informative, particularly given that some differences were observed by career stage. Socialization factors (e.g., gender and socioeconomic status) may impact success perceptions, but they may also change over time, particularly in line with cognitive dissonance theory if a person is unable to realize previous conceptions of success.

Conclusion

Although the race effects were modest in magnitude, the consistent discretion of these differences should caution employers to be vigilant in their attempt to assure equal opportunity. Organizations should periodically examine the project managers' job performance evaluations, advancement experiences and career attitudes for possible differences based on race. The presence of race differences in any of the variables should be carefully scrutinized to identify underlying causes and to determine whether these differences reflect unfair treatment. The importance of establishing an unbiased performance rating system cannot be overemphasized, given the dominant role of ratings in shaping future advancement opportunities.

Despite the variety of approaches in measuring career success and in particular subjective and objective career success, we conclude that there are several arguments from the literature that it might be advisable to assess both aspects of career success. As pointed out by Hall (1996) individuals do not necessarily approach their career decisions rationally. Thus, one's subjective perception might influence how one's career has and/or will proceed. In other words: objective success could influence how individuals subjectively experience their career success, but subjective experiences of success might also

influence individual objective as subjective success could make a person self-confident or it could enhance his or her motivation and goal-striving. These motivational effects could, in turn, lead to more objective success over time. Alternatively, people experience objective success, consequently, subjectively develop their understanding about what constitutes career success, then individually act upon, and eventually leading to certain (more successful) outcomes. The positive relation between objective success upon job satisfaction has indeed been confirmed by empirical research. Despite the scarcity of results of the influence of subjective success on objective success Marks and Fleming (1999) found that subjective well-being predicted income. Abele and Spurk (2009a) show that subjective success highly contributes to objective success.

Furthermore, the subjective meaning of objective and subjective career success depend on gender and age. As shown age is positively related to job satisfaction. Thus, the individual meaning of career success might also depend on one's point in life. While younger adults might still strive for objective career success changes such as marriage and children might put one's emphasis on subjective aspects of career success. Flexibility, autonomy, and satisfaction within the professional and private sphere might gain more importance and the traditional linear career path might be put to the side.

This is closely related to the influence of gender on one's career. Previous research, for instance, found that women's career development remains more complex than men's because of their multiple families and work-related roles. Additionally, the results suggest that men tend to have more linear, traditional career patterns placing more emphasis on monetary rewards and promotion compared to their female counterparts. This is supported by several scholars who all reported that most women valued the balance between work and personal life higher than men.

In essence, I agree with Abele that career satisfaction is indeed concerned with career success because from an overall perspective life-success is about being content with one's job, career path, and personal life.

References

- Abele-Brehm, A., and Stief, M. "Die Prognose des Berufserfolgs von Hochschulabsolventinnen und -absolventen: Befunde zur ersten und zweiten Erhebung der Erlanger Längsschnittstudie BELA-E." *Zeitschrift für Arbeits- und Organisationspsychologie* 48, no. 1 (2004): 4–16.
- Abele, A. E., and Spurk, D. "How do objective and subjective career success interrelate over time?" *Journal for Occupational and Organizational Psychology* 82, no. 4 (2009a): 803–824.

Abele, A. E., and Spurk, D. "The longitudinal impact of self-efficacy and career goals on objective and subjective career success." *Journal of Vocational Behavior* 74, no. 1(2009b): 53–62.

Alderfer, C. P., Alderfer, C. J., Tucker, I., & Tucker, R. 1980. Diagnosing race relations in management. *Journal of Applied Behavioral Science*, 27: 135- 166.

Arthur, M., Khapova, S., & Wilderom, C. (2005). Career Success in a Boundaryless career world. *Journal of Organizational Behavior*, 26, 177–202.

Brown, H. A., & Ford, D. L., Jr. 1977. Older minorities – "roadblocked" in the organization. *Business Horizons*, 17(3): 27-36. Crotty, P. T., & Timmons, J.A. 1974. Older minorities – "roadblocked" in the organization. *Business Horizons*, 17(3): 27-36.

Davis, G., & Watson, G. 1982. *Black life in corporate America. Swimming in the mainstream.* New York: Doubleday.

Detle, D. E., Abele, A. E., and Renner, O. "Zur Definition und Messung von Berufserfolg: Theoretische Überlegungen und metaanalytische Befunde zum Zusammenhang von externen und internen Laufbahnerfolgsmäßen." *Zeitschrift für Personalpsychologie* 3, no. 4 (2004): 170–183.

Dickens, F., & Dickens, J. B. 1982. *The Black Manager: Making it in the corporate world.* New York: AMACOM.

DiTomaso, N., Thompson, D. E., & Blake, D. H. 1986. Corporate perspectives on minority advancement in management. Paper presented at the 46th Annual Meeting of the Academy of Management, Chicago.

Fernandez, J. P. 1975. *Black managers in white corporations.* New York: Wiley.

Fernandez, J. P. 1981. *Racism and sexism in corporate life: Changing values in American business.* Lexington, Mass.: Lexington Books.

Greenhaus, J. (2003). Career dynamics. In Borman, W., Ilgen, D., & Klimoski, R. (Eds.), *Handbook of psychology: Industrial and organizational psychology* (Vol. 12, pp. 519–540). New York: Wiley.

Hall, D. (1976). *Careers in organizations.* Pacific Palisades, CA.: Goodyear

Hall, D. T. "Protean careers of the 21st century." *Academy of Management Executive* 10, no. 4 (1996): 8–16.

Harlan, A., & Weiss, C. L. 1982. Sex differences in factors affecting managerial career advancement. In P. A. Wallace (Ed.), *Women in the workplace*: 59: 100. Boston: Auburn House.

- Heslin, P. (2003). Self- and other-referent criteria of career success. *Journal of Career Assessment*, 11, 262–286.
- Heslin, P. (2005). Conceptualizing and evaluating career success. *Journal of Organizational Behavior*, 26, 113–136.
- Ilgén, D. R., & Youtz, M. A. 1986. Factors affecting the evaluation and development of minorities in the organization. In K. Rowland & G. Ferris (Eds.), *Research in personnel and human resource management: A research annual*: 307-337. Greenwich Conn.: JAI Press.
- Irons, E., & Moore, G., Q. 1985. *Black managers in the banking industry*. New York: Praeger.
- Jones, E. 1986. Black Managers: The dream deferred. *Harvard Business Review*, 64 (3): 84-93.
- Kanter, R. M. 1979. Differential access to opportunity and power. In Alvarez (Ed.), *Discrimination in organizations*: 52 – 68. San Francisco: Jossey-Bass.
- Kraiger, K., & Ford, J. K. 1985. A meta-analysis of rate race effects in performance ratings. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 70: 56- 65.
- Levitin, T., Quinn, R. P., & Staines, G. L. 1971. Sex discrimination against the American working woman. *American Behavioral Scientist*, 15: 238-254.
- Marks, G. N., and Fleming, N. "Influences and consequences of well-being among Australian young people: 1980-1995." *Social Indicators Research* 46, no. 3 (1999): 301–323.
- Ng, T., Eby, L., Sorenson, K., & Feldman, D. (2005). Predictors of objective and subjective career success. *Personnel Psychology*, 58, 367–408.
- Morrison, A. M., White, R. P., & Van Velsor, E. 1987. *Breaking the glass ceiling*. Reading Mass.: Addison-Wesley.
- Nixon, R. 1985a. *Climbing the corporate ladder: Some perceptions among black managers*. Washington, D.C.: National Urban League.
- Olson, C. A., & Becker, B. E. 1983. Sex discrimination in the promotion process. *Industrial and Labor Relations Review*, 36: 624-641.
- Project Management Institute, (2008). *A Guide to the Project Management Body of Knowledge*. 4th Edition
- Rosen, B., Templeton, N. C., & Kichline, K. 1981. First few years in the job: Women in management. *Business Horizons*, 24(6) 26-29.
- Shockley, Ureksoy, Rodopman, Poteat, & Dullaghan, (2016). Development of a new scale to measure subjective career success: A mixed-methods study; pp. 3, 4.

Stewart, L. P., & Gudykunst, W. B. 1982. Differential factors influencing the hierarchical level and several promotions of males and females within an organization. *Academy of Management Journal*, 25: 586-5977.

Terborg, J. R., & Ilgen, D. R. 1975. A theoretical approach to sex discrimination in traditionally masculine occupations. *Organizational Behavior and Human Performance*, 13: 352-376.

Turban, D., & Dougherty, T. (1994). Role of protégé personality in receipt of mentoring and career success. *Academy of Management Journal*, 37, 688–702.

Williams, L. 1987. For the black professional, the obstacles remain. *New York Times*, July 14: A16.

Wolf, W. C., & Fligstein, N. D. 1979. Sex and authority in the workplace: The causes of sexual inequality. *American Sociological Review*, 44: 235-254.

Wysocki, K. R., (2012). *Effective Project Management. Traditional, Agile, Extreme.*

Zhou, W., Sun, J., Guan, Y., Li, Y., & Pan, J. (2013). Criteria of career success among Chinese employees: Developing a multidimensional scale with qualitative and quantitative approaches. *Journal of Career Assessment*, 21(2), 265–277.

Shilimi Moono

Bachelor’s degree in Business Administration, majoring in Computer Information System. Currently MBA student at Chang’An University, China.

Yibin Li

Lecturer at Chang’An University
Title: Associate Professor, Doctor/Postdoctoral, Master's Tutor,
Member of China Logistics Society
Research Areas: Logistics and Supply Chain Management and
Evolution of Logistics Cluster

© 2019 by the authors. TWASP, NY, USA. Author/authors are fully responsible for the text, figure, data in above pages. This article is an open access article distributed under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>)

